

Real and synthetic scenarios generated for the development, training, virtual testing and validation of CCAM systems

SYNERGIES

D1.5 Initial Exploitation Plan

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Funded through the Horizon Europe program, the SYNERGIES project is a Research and Innovation Action (RIA). RIA focuses on activities to discover new knowledge and explore opportunities to improve technology, products, processes, services or solutions through small-scale prototypes in laboratory or simulated environments [1].

The SYNERGIES project aims to achieve collectively six Key Results (KRs), altogether with individual ones obtained by each of the 33 partners. Depending on the collective KR, the expected maturity level to be reached varies between Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) five and six. However, to avoid that no one is interested to continue maintaining and using the KRs when the project ends, Task 1.3 on Innovation, Exploitation and IPR Management (T1.3) is focused to leverage the project legacy.

Design an effective innovative strategy to exploit the KRs and a plan to solve intellectual property rights (IPR) conflicts are the objectives of T1.3. As part of Work Package 1 (WP1), T1.3 evaluates in this report, called *D1.5 Initial Exploitation Plan*, alternatives of exploitation considering multiple perspectives. These also include additional details on the collective and individual results. As the project evolves, such evaluation requires to be complemented with lessons learnt, tools and any other outcome obtained. Since D1.5 will also require to be adapted to market changes, stakeholders' needs and beneficiaries' inputs, a final version will be reflected in the *D1.6 Final Exploitation Plan* at the end of the project. Therefore, the D1.5 submitted in the sixth month of the project is focused on innovation and exploitation, deferring the IPR analysis until the results are more mature.

The basis of the D1.5 is the signed Grant Agreement (GA), supported by the definition of exploitation to clarify the objective of the present report. While the GA in Part B delimits the project scope, objectives, key results, including the specific T1.3 description, it is from the European Research Executive Agency (REA) that the definition of exploitation has been sourced [2] - *“using results in developing, creating and marketing or improving a product, process, or service, or shaping a policy that could have a positive impact on the public's quality of life.”* -. Consequently, D1.5, and subsequent D1.6, aim to devise exploitation alternatives to ensure that project results are used with a positive impact and that IPR are protected in the long term. However, such ambitions can be limited by complexities and barriers proper of competition, stakeholders' interests, resources assigned to each task and business goals. Furthermore, some aspects are only partially covered in this report since they are expected to be complemented by Task 6.2, with the business models assessment starting in month twelve.

The work performed in the D1.5 begins defining the long- and short-term objectives in chapter 2, detailing also the process of exploitation of the expected results. Chapter 3 covers the opportunities for strategic collaboration, identifying specific entities and European-funded projects additionally extending the description of collective and individual results, resulting in an exploitation plan aligned with the project milestones. D1.5 concludes with the Chapter 4.

Keywords: Exploitation, CCAM, Key Results

2 OBJECTIVES

The definitive objective of T1.3 is to utilize project results for commercial, societal, and policy-making purposes. Objective expected to be achieved by promoting and adapting project results to user's needs, complemented by the monitoring of market needs and technical evolutions to maximize their exploitation.

In the long term, the T1.3 objective is linked to the progressive accomplishment of expected outcomes following the project conclusion. For this reason, it will be essential to collaborate with entities, initiatives and projects that are working on CCAM systems, scenarios and databases. The ambition is that European stakeholders use the SYNERGIES project results to enable the achievement of the following expected outcomes:

1. Improved validation of CCAM systems, enabled by real and synthetic test scenarios, along with the widest possible coverage of traffic situations that CCAM systems can encounter on European roads.
2. Efficient provision of relevant test scenarios in a permanently updated and therefore dynamic EU wide database.
3. Accelerated AI development and training making use of the dynamic scenario database.
4. Use of the most appropriate approaches (e.g., vehicle-based versus (quasi-) stationary sensor units), to record relevant traffic data, as a basis for the derivation of test scenarios, in different traffic environments according to extending ODDs.
5. Commitment from key stakeholders to the validation methodology, the scenario database, and its usage and to the provision of significant volumes of raw data and/or scenarios extracted from such data.

In the short term, the T1.3 objective is to coordinate strategic actions of active cooperation and to identify exploitation opportunities where the project key results can be relevant. An additional objective is to potentialize the tools, new knowledge, lessons learned, methodologies and created standards, as well as the solutions that emerged from the beneficiaries. Consequently, the main objective of the D1.5 is the design of an initial exploitation plan, based on identified entities, beneficiaries' perspectives and key results. The plan will later require to be discussed, validated, and complemented throughout the project.

The specific objectives of the D1.5 gravitate around the six key exploitable results, and their potential users, or interested parties. However, considering the difficulty detailing the usage currently, D1.5 proposes to use the information collaboratively to benefit all the project activities. In addition, D1.5 will plan co-creation activities and workshops that are favourable for both stakeholders and the project. Figure 1 provides an overview of the T1.3 strategy.

Figure 1. SYNERGIES Project - T1.3 High-level Description of Exploitation and IPR Strategy

3 DESCRIPTION OF WORK

Focused on the project scope, the present chapter begins detailing opportunities to maximize the impact of the KRs. Then, it continues extending the description of the collective and individual results considering observations given by partners and WP leaders. Finally, it defines an exploitation plan aligned with the milestones to be achieved by the project.

3.1 Maximizing the Impact of Key Results

Collaboration and promotion are key components to maximize the project impact. In that sense, section 3.1 is the starting point of the exploitation plan, to ensure that external and internal discussions refine project results to tailor and meet users' needs. The approach builds from the general description given to the key results during the proposal phase (see Section 3.2.1) and then it aligns with the project scope, beneficiary's responsibilities and resources assigned. Table 1 presents the identified primary users of the key results detailed in section 3.2.

Users	Key Results (KR)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - OEMs - Tiers - Researchers/CCAM EU Projects - Consumer assessment - DB owners - Type Approval authorities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - KR1 SYNERGIES platform (Scenario Dataspace and Marketplace) - KR2. Open datasets from heterogeneous sources to ensure coverage in training for AI algorithms - KR3. Best practices for data gathering & Scenario extraction and identification - KR4. Data processing tools - KR5. Stakeholder engagement, international cooperation & promotion to standardisation - KR6. Governance tools

Table 1. SYNERGIES Project - Identified Users and Key Results

3.1.1 Broad Opportunities for Leveraging Key Results

There are individuals and entities, both public and private, interested in the technologies, services, knowledge, and solutions that the SYNERGIES project aims to deliver. These stakeholders, whether they act as enablers, partners, or competitors, can influence the long-term success of the project positively or negatively. They may share similar interests in the project's outcomes or oppose them due to competitive or business reasons. The primary goal is to raise their awareness of the project's objectives and to gather feedback on how the project's results can continuously support their processes and activities.

3.1.1.1 European Level

The European Commission launched initiatives such as the Common European Data spaces [3], the European strategy for data [4], and the European data market [5], directly related to all SYNERGIES KR. Technically, the possibilities of exploitation are open in relation to KR2, KR3 and KR4, where the collection, analysis, management and cooperative use of data are gaining relevance. SYNERGIES project ensures the European vision of data spaces through the KR1, developing a platform and an openly accessible marketplace for scenario generation, and database governance that enables the integration of new initiatives. Additional opportunities are presented in Table 2.

CCAM Data needs	Opportunities for Exploiting the Key Results
Standardized Data Formats	KR2, KR3, KR4 - Enforces the use of standardized data formats across different sources, ensuring consistency and compatibility.
Automated Data Cleaning	KR2, KR3, KR4 - Automates tasks like removing duplicates, handling missing values, and correcting errors, essential for data normalization.
Real-Time Data Processing	KR2, KR3, KR4 - Processes and normalizes data in real-time, ensuring up-to-date and accurate data for simulations.
Integration of Diverse Data Sources	KR2, KR3, KR4 - Integrates data from various sources, normalizing it to a common format for comprehensive analysis and simulation.
Scenario-Based Normalization	KR2, KR3, KR4 - Tailors' data normalization processes to specific simulation scenarios, ensuring relevant and appropriately formatted data.

Table 2. Opportunities for the Key results in Data Normalization

3.1.1.2 National Level

At the national level, government agencies are releasing regulations and policies to operate or test automated vehicles (AV) to facilitate the evolution of this technology for the benefit of end users. Table 3 presents examples of this tendency, including countries such as UK, Germany, and France. These countries have already publicly clarified legal aspects to introduce and adopt AV. This trend is required to be followed by other countries and is expected by both OEMs and related stakeholders. Until AV commercialization, the authorization, licensing, and operation require to continue being clarified through innovative tools, that ease and speed up the process. SYNERGIES KR have multiple opportunities in this area, as the KR1 enabling government agencies to evaluate specific scenarios where a regulation or policy is applicable, or the KR6 relevant for-type approval or certification given a prescribed ODD for example.

Country	Year	Name	Opportunities for Exploiting the Key Results
United Kingdom	2024	Automated Vehicles (AV) Act [6]	KR1 - Evaluation of the legal framework for regulating the use of automated vehicles on roads and other public places

Country	Year	Name	Opportunities for Exploiting the Key Results
Germany	2021	Autonomous Driving Act [7]	KR1 - Evaluation of the operation of level 4 of automated vehicles
France	2019	Loi d'Orientation des Mobilités (LOM) [8]	KR1 - Evaluation of the testing and deployment of autonomous vehicles.

Table 3. Automated Vehicles Regulation and Policies Released by UK, Germany, France

3.1.1.3 Local Level

At the local level, public entities such as traffic management centres and road operators require to ensure safety in urban, interurban and national roads when AV are introduced. Simultaneously, they need to use economic and technical resources wisely, ensuring that investments are cost-effective, technologies are up-to-date, and operations are efficient to maximize the benefits. Consequently, Table 4 lists opportunities where the KRs can be applicable to benefit public entities. For instance, KR1 can be used to support cities in the identification of critical zones since a reduction of the devices required to support AV impacts installation and maintenance costs, in addition to supporting infrastructure planning and policy development.

Benefits for Public Entities	Opportunities for Exploiting the Key Results
Identification of Critical Zones	KR1, KR3, KR4 - The platform can simulate traffic patterns and identify areas where AV need additional information due to bad road surface marking for example, helping cities prioritize the installation of infrastructure sensors and save costs.
Infrastructure Planning	KR1, KR3, KR4 - Cities can use simulations to plan and test new infrastructure projects, ensuring they meet the needs of automated and connected vehicles before actual implementation.
Emergency Response Optimization	KR1, KR3, KR4 - The platform can simulate emergency scenarios, helping cities develop and refine emergency response plans to ensure quick and effective action.
Policy Development	KR1, KR5, KR6 - Cities can use simulation data to inform policy decisions, such as setting speed limits, zoning regulations, and other rules that support the safe and efficient operation of automated vehicles.
Community Engagement	KR1 - Simulations can be used to demonstrate the benefits and impacts of automated vehicle projects to the public, fostering community support and understanding.

Table 4. Identified Benefits of the SYNERGIES Key Results for Public Entities

3.1.1.4 Homologation

The process of homologation in the automotive industry is summarized in the steps presented in Table 5. The process ensures compliance with regulatory standards before vehicles, systems, and components are marketed and used. There are specialized organizations and agencies are accredited to conduct tests to inspect and certify work with OEMs and Tiers in that process. Accounting that a process may be valid for ensuring technical specifications, the question is how organizations and agencies can ensure that AV behave appropriately in any situation to guarantee safety of road users? A possibility is to use the KR1 to identify and certify the conditions in which AV can be used. Furthermore, the operation of AV based on additional specifications such as road type, locations, and speed can be crucial conditions. The use of the KRs can be extended also to the possibilities explained below.

Key Steps in Homologation	Opportunities for Exploiting the Key Results
Initial Assessment	KR1 - The platform can simulate various regulatory environments, helping OEMs understand and prepare for different market requirements.
Testing and Certification	KR1 - Simulations can replicate real-world conditions to test safety, emissions, and performance, reducing the need for physical prototypes and accelerating the testing phase.
Documentation	KR2, KR3, KR4 - Automated data collection and reporting features in the platform can streamline the preparation of technical reports and compliance documentation.
Approval	KR1 - The platform can provide detailed simulation results and compliance evidence, making it easier to demonstrate adherence to regulatory standards to authorities.
Research and understanding	KR1 - Continuous updates and scenario simulations can keep OEMs informed about changes in regulations and emerging standards in different markets.
Local Partnerships	KR1, KR5, KR6 - The platform can facilitate collaboration with local regulatory bodies by providing a shared environment for testing and validation.
Standardization and Adaptation	KR1 - Simulations can help OEMs design products that meet global standards and then adapt them for specific markets, ensuring compliance with local regulations.
Regular Audits and Updates	KR1 - The platform can be used for ongoing monitoring and re-testing to ensure continued compliance as regulations evolve.

Table 5. Opportunities of the Key Results in the Homologation Process

3.1.2 Targeted Entities and Strategic Collaborations

There are multiple entities focused on transport, regulations, testing, and deployment. Each entity has its own goals and has made progress in its respective field. These identified entities have been considered for strategic collaboration to address the various challenges faced by both them and the project. Collaboration is also addressed to exploit the KRs, to promote achievements, to exchange knowledge, and to drive technical advancements. The list also includes EU-funded projects investigating topics, such as digital twins, scenario identification, and new data analysis procedures, which are of interest to the SYNERGIES project. These identified entities and EU-funded projects are expected to be contacted at different project stages.

3.1.2.1 European Entities

Table 6 covers a list of European entities among associations, organizations and platforms that use transport data, that potentially could be used for CCAM purposes. Some of them already signed a collaboration agreement to standardise and deliver safety-related traffic information in Europe [9]. The list includes standardization entities able to use KRs to facilitate and to reduce the time in which standards are produced. These entities can be subdivided into sub-groups dedicated to CCAM, an aspect to be further clarified throughout the project, as well as their potential involvement.

Entity	Objective
Traveller Information Services Association (TISA)	Information sourced from [9]: International association that leads the development of trusted traffic & travel standards and harmonized services. Focuses on implementation of traffic and travel information services and products based on existing standards.
National Access Point Coordination Organisation for Europe (NAPCORE)	Information sourced from [10]: Organisation that coordinates and harmonise more than 30 mobility data platforms across Europe. NAPCORE increases access and expands availability to mobility related data by coordinated data access and better harmonisation of the European NAPs. NAPCORE empowers NAPs and National Bodies by defining and implementing common procedures and strategies, strengthening the position and the role of NAPs, supporting steps towards the creation of pan-European solutions to better facilitate the use of EU-wide data.
DATEX II Organization	Information sourced from [11]: Electronic language used in Europe for the exchange of traffic information and traffic data. DATEX II supports two closely related use cases: The provision of information from data source to data consumer on one hand, and the support of joint traffic management operations of collaboration competent authorities on the other. The stakeholder cooperation maintaining DATEX II is now in the NAPCORE project

Entity	Objective
CAR 2 CAR Communication Consortium (C2C-CC)	Information sourced from [12]: (C2C-CC) aims at assisting towards accident-free traffic (vision zero). It further aims at supporting the highest safety level at improved traffic efficiency anywhere, anytime at the lowest cost to the end user and the environment. While working on solutions supporting all driving levels from manual to fully automated it considers specific needs of stakeholders, types of vehicles and users. The C2C-CC contributes to the development and specification of robust and reliable solutions that allow for a continuous and seamless evolution of required functionalities.
Data for Road Safety ecosystem (DFRS)	Information sourced from [13]: DFRS ecosystem is to improve road safety by maximizing the reach of safety-related traffic information powered by safety data generated by vehicles and road infrastructure operators. Alerts generated by vehicles, along with infrastructure data, are shared using a decentralised data collaboration architecture.
C-Roads	Information sourced from [14]: The C-Roads Platform is a joint initiative of European Member States and road operators deploying C-ITS services across Europe to significantly improve the exchange of information between vehicles and road infrastructure. The C-Roads Platform currently unites 18 European Member States' driven pilots and deployment entities on C-ITS services working jointly on the strategic and coordinated implementation.
TN-ITS	Information sourced from [15]: Multi-stakeholder innovation platform that creates a data chain mechanism for trusted authoritative spatial road data changes, between road authorities and map makers & services providers. TN-ITS enhances Road Safety, Transport Efficiency, Automation and applications such as MaaS, Smart Parking, Cycling.

Entity	Objective
CEN and CENELEC	<p>Information sourced from [16]:</p> <p>The European Committee for Standardization (CEN) and the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization (CENELEC) are two distinct private international non-profit organizations.</p> <p>The European Committee for Standardization is one of three European Standardization Organizations (together with CENELEC and ETSI) that have been officially recognized by the European Union and by the European Free Trade Association (EFTA) as being responsible for developing and defining voluntary standards at European level.</p> <p>CEN's National Members are the National Standardization Bodies (NSBs) of the 27 European Union countries, United Kingdom, the Republic of North Macedonia, Serbia and Türkiye plus three countries of the European Free Trade Association (Iceland, Norway and Switzerland). There is one member per country.</p>
ETSI	<p>Information sourced from [17]:</p> <p>ETSI (European Telecommunications Standards Institute) supports the development, ratification and testing of globally applicable standards for ICT-enabled systems, applications and services.</p> <p>Includes supporting European regulations and legislation through the creation of Harmonised European Standards. Only standards developed by the three ESOs (CEN, CENELEC and ETSI) are recognized as European Standards (ENs).</p>

Table 6. SYNERGIES Project Strategic Collaborations with European Entities

3.1.2.2 European Funded Projects

The following assessment considers the information contained in the Community Research and Development Information Service (CORDIS). This platform is the European Commission's primary source of EU-funded project results within EU's framework programmes for research and innovation, from FP1 to Horizon Europe [18].

Including SYNERGIES project, there are currently 37 active European projects to accelerate the adoption, development, and deployment of CCAM. Most of them (17) will end in 2025, and 10 will conclude in 2027 (Table 7). Discussions and agreements are required to design a collaborative exploitation strategy with the goal to use the results produced by projects that end parallelly to SYNERGIES, as well as the exploitation of key results from the projects that are finalising.

Project end Year	Number of Active CCAM Projects
2024	1

Project end Year	Number of Active CCAM Projects
2025	17
2026	7
2027	11
2028	1
Grand Total	37

Table 7. CORDIS - Horizon Europe CCAM Projects Ending From 2024 to 2028

SYNERGIES project encompasses scenario, testing, data, and standards and requires the identification which of the analysed CCAM EU-Funded projects are related most to the project scope. Table 8 contains a summary of the potential benefits that can be obtained collaborating with those projects and prioritises which ones should be contacted first. A complete assessment is presented in Appendix A.

Project end Year	Project acronym	Strategic Alignment with SYNERGIES (Low, Medium, High)	Potential Benefits
2024	UNLOCK-CEI	Low	-Datasets
2025	AI4CCAM	Medium	-Simulation of AV with road users in three use cases.
2025	Althena	Medium	-CCAM scenarios and use cases. -Datasets: Real/synthetic data management.
2025	AUGMENTED CCAM	High	- CCAM Scenarios and use cases: 7 test sites across 3 European Countries -Datasets
2025	AWARE2ALL	High	- CCAM scenarios and use cases -Datasets -Methodology of a safety framework
2025	CONDUCTOR	Medium	-Simulation models and tools -Data fusion
2025	CONNECT	High	-User needs -Datasets, data exchange, data space modelling - Data authorization and authentication process
2025	EVENTS	High	-CCAM scenarios and use cases
2025	FAME	Medium	-Methodology for testing
2025	i4Driving	High	- CCAM scenarios and use cases -Datasets -Simulation results -Methodologies
2025	IN2CCAM	High	- CCAM scenarios and use cases: living labs in Tampere, Trikala, Turin, Vigo, Bari and Quadrilatero. -Datasets - CCAM KPIs - Standards: interoperability framework and open standards

Project end Year	Project acronym	Strategic Alignment with SYNERGIES (Low, Medium, High)	Potential Benefits
2025	MAIA	Medium	- CCAM scenarios and use cases: airport infrastructure and the remaining access modes
2025	Move2CCAM	High	-CCAM Scenarios and use cases descriptions -Datasets and data collection tools -CCAM KPIs
2025	PoDIUM	High	-CCAM Scenarios and use cases: Living labs in Germany, Italy and Spain, in urban, highway and cross-border environments. -Datasets, data collection/processing
2025	SELFY	Low	-Datasets and data collection tools
2025	SINFONICA	Medium	-Users' needs -CCAM Scenarios and use cases
2025	SUNRISE	High	-Users' needs through the expert network -Methodology of Safety Assurance Framework
2025	V4SAFETY	Medium	-Methodology for evaluation and comparison of safety measures for CCAM -Standards and policies for road safety
2026	BERTHA	High	- CCAM scenarios and use cases: Mixed traffic - Datasets: Design and analysis of CCAM components, digitally (OEMs, Tiers)
2026	CCAM-ERAS	Low	-No direct relation with the project
2026	KEYSTONE	High	-Data exchange for transport enforcement of authorities
2026	MODI	High	-CCAM scenarios and use cases (Logistics): Public roads on the corridor from Rotterdam to Oslo. -Datasets
2026	ROADVIEW	High	-CCAM Scenarios and use cases: Under Complex environment and traffic conditions. -Datasets
2026	SETO	Medium	-Standards for smart enforcement of transport
2026	ULTIMO	High	- CCAM scenarios and use cases: 3 test sites in Europe 15 or more multi-vendor SAE L4 AVs per site. - Datasets
2027	AUTOMOTIF	High	- CCAM scenarios and use cases (Logistics) -Datasets -Simulations - Standards
2027	AutoTRUST	Medium	- CCAM scenarios and use cases: interaction between users and new automated modes - Datasets - Standards

Project end Year	Project acronym	Strategic Alignment with SYNERGIES (Low, Medium, High)	Potential Benefits
2027	CulturalRoad	Low	- User needs: Participatory planning to adopt CCAM
2027	Diversify - CCAM	Low	- CCAM scenarios and use cases: 12 pilot sites in six EU countries. (CCAM Acceptance) -Platform
2027	EvoRoads	High	-Methodologies: Safety assessment framework -Platform: Validation across seven locations in Europe,
2027	FRODDO	High	- CCAM Scenarios and use cases: ODDs design with authorities and operators -Datasets
2027	iDriving	Medium	- CCAM scenarios and use cases: TRL 6 prototype -Datasets
2027	metaCCAZE	High	- CCAM scenarios and use cases: Passenger and freight services -Datasets: 4 cities (Amsterdam, Munich, Limassol, Tampere). 6 follower cities (Athens, Krakow, Gonzo, Milan, Miskolc, Paris region) - Governance models
2027	OptiPEX	High	- CCAM Scenarios and use cases (Passengers, wheelchair users and tourists) -Datasets: 3 living labs
2027	PLIADES	High	-Data space -Data sharing: novel AI-based brokers and connectors using extended metadata -Cross-domain AI connectors:
2028	MOBILITIES FOR EU	Medium	- CCAM Scenarios and use cases: -Datasets: Madrid, Dresden, Ioaninna-Greece, Trencin-Slovakia, Espoo-Finland, Gdansk-Poland and Sarajevo-Bosnia&Herzegovina

Table 8. CORDIS - Evaluation of CCAM projects Focused on SYNERGIES Interests

3.2 Exploitable Key Results of the Project

Among the project key results there are solutions, tools and new knowledge produced to solve or clarify identified issues. The latter consolidated in the SYNERGIES project summary as the absence of interoperable scenario databases, time-consuming and expensive development cycles, and regulatory ambiguities. The project solves them through six KRs complemented by the Safety Assurance Framework developed in HEADSTART [19] and SUNRISE [20] projects.

From all the KRs, the summary highlights a European platform designed to enhance the development, training, virtual testing, and validation of CCAM systems called the SYNERGIES Platform. The platform comprises a Scenario Dataspace, aligned with Europe's approach to data sharing and competitiveness, and a Marketplace, ensuring continual updates and dataspace

scalability. In addition to exploit the platform new initiatives can included into the scenario dataspace, offering the requisite tools and guidance, from data processing and scenario identification to scenario database governance. The identified users of the platform and KRs are mentioned in Table 1, and are extended to also include their exploitation to the ones identified in sections 3.1.1 and 3.1.2 respectively.

Considering that SYNERGIES project is a RIA, the promised technological capabilities of the final versions of the KRs are between TRL five and six. As a reference, the following overview aims to clarify expected functionalities that can be explained to potential users to avoid false expectations.

- TRL 5 - Technology tested in a simulated environment closely to real-world conditions.
- TRL 6 - Fully functional prototype tested in similar conditions to where it will be used.

3.2.1 Collective Key Results

The six KRs to be achieved collectively by project partners are described below, with a clarification on the aspects related to the components used and challenges faced in the first six months. This collaborative process will continue, as there are multiple technological details that need to be addressed. WP leaders have provided short descriptions for each of the KRs, based on their involvement, progress and discussions.

3.2.1.1 KR1. SYNERGIES Platform

SYNERGIES aims to create a unique platform for scenario-based validation in the domain of CCAM. By adopting a federated organizational model, leveraged from SUNRISE, individual entities are being united, maximizing their potential through collaboration and resource optimization. The validation process considers the use of the Safety Assurance Framework developed by SUNRISE. The project is developing an openly accessible marketplace, offering cutting-edge tools for data processing (WP4), scenario generation (WP5), and database governance (WP6), fostering seamless scalability, and enabling the integration of new entities. The platform's success expects to revolutionize the validation process, empowering stakeholders and advancing the reliability and safety of CCAM systems, contributing to a safer and smarter transportation landscape.

- From TRL5 to TRL6

The KR continues to clarify specific aspects, as described below:

- WP3 - The assessment of data gaps and limitations (T3.1, T3.2) depends on the platform scope and requirements.
- WP5 - It is contributing to the tools for scenario generation to the SYNERGIES platform marketplace. The tools consider the knowledge-based and/or data-based methods. Depending on the underlying method of each tool, the tool may need certain input data, which is not included in the SYNERGIES platform. The output of the tools are scenarios that may be stored in the SYNERGIES platform scenario dataspace. For the tools to be useful for more than one data source, there must be a common data format for the input data that is used by the tools. In addition, there must be a common scenario format for the scenarios to be generated. For this point, a synchronisation with SUNRISE is crucial.
- WP6 - "Governance, sustainability and representativeness" is essential for creating a unique platform for scenario-based validation of CCAM systems by ensuring data quality, standardization, and compliance. It facilitates controlled data sharing, enables quantification of aspects of the scenario data, such as its coverage and representativeness

with respect to an Operational Design Domain (ODD), and provides traceability, which are all crucial for accurate and reliable safety assurance of CCAM systems.

- WP7 - SYNERGIES Platform establishment, testing and delivery is responsible for integrating, testing, and delivering the SYNERGIES Platform. It ensures that all components and tools from other work packages work together seamlessly, tests the Platform to verify functionality and robustness, and adapts and improves the platform based on feedback. WP7 provides stakeholders with tools for data processing, scenario generation, and database governance.
- WP8 - it is contributing to achieving KR1 by ensuring the quality, usability, and completeness of the tools for collecting and processing datasets. Specifically, it will establish an evaluation framework (T8.1), gather input from end-users (T8.2), analyse the effectiveness of the tools (T8.3), and identify areas for further improvement (T8.4).

3.2.1.2 KR2. Open datasets from heterogeneous sources

The consortium members are detailing the most comprehensive set of scenarios available. SYNERGIES is identifying the existing gaps and collect further data using vehicles, infrastructure, and drones (WP3) to be then processed and provided into the scenario dataspace. Resulting in the most complete source of data for CCAM validation, aligned with a harmonised approach and leveraging from previous activities.

- From TRL4 to TRL6

The KR continues to clarify specific aspects, as described below:

- WP3 - A data listing of available datasets is being created including open datasets, datasets generated in relevant projects, and datasets from SYNERGIES partners. A methodology for qualification of these datasets will be designed and applied to select those datasets that fulfil the scope and requirements of SYNERGIES. Identification of gaps and limitations will inform the data collection and generation to achieve a comprehensive and representative database from which the scenarios will be extracted.
- WP5 - It will assist in the selection of the open datasets suitable for the SYNERGIES project's activities in terms of checking whether they are applicable for the scenario methodology to be used.
- WP7 - Ensures functionality of the SYNERGIES Platform, which will process and manage the set of scenarios provided by the consortium members. By integrating tools for data processing and scenario generation, WP7 enables the identification and filling of data gaps using inputs from vehicles, infrastructure, and drones. This results in a robust Scenario Dataspace that offers the complete and harmonized source of data for CCAM validation.

3.2.1.3 KR3. Best practices for data gathering & scenario extraction and identification

SYNERGIES is developing a methodology and guidelines for assessing data from heterogeneous sources (WP3) based on their suitability for high-quality scenario creation. Additionally, SYNERGIES develops and harmonises scenario identification and extraction methods to consolidate existing approaches from previous activities to ensure their interoperability (WP5). These methods contribute to identifying and extracting scenarios for different specific use cases and from various data sources.

- From TRL3 to TRL5

The KR continues to clarify specific aspects, as described below:

- WP3 - The available datasets will be evaluated based on several qualification metrics to assess if they can be used for scenario generation according to the SYNERGIES platform and stakeholder requirements. It is expected to produce a taxonomy of existing datasets with qualification scores that will be useful as a guideline for data collection and generation T3.3: In coordination with WP5, quality requirements for recording trajectory data are defined, which are required for the generation of high-quality scenarios. T3.5: Derive quality metrics for AI generated data from data requirements defined by T3.1.
- WP5 - It provides scenarios for domains which are not covered as much by the current data sources (e.g., rare weather conditions). These scenarios are provided: (i) by identifying and extracting them from real-world data (coming from WP3) and (ii) by generating them based on knowledge and/or data yielding scenarios that have not necessarily been seen in collected real-world data.
- WP7 - it is supporting the project by ensuring the SYNERGIES Platform effectively integrates and utilizes the methodologies and guidelines developed in WP3 and WP5. WP7 ensures that these methods are harmonized and interoperable, consolidating existing approaches from previous activities.

3.2.1.4 KR4. Data processing tools

SYNERGIES is developing and implementing a semi-automatic annotation system that implements cutting-edge trustworthy machine learning (ML) methodologies that boost the automatic annotation task with a web-based interface to facilitate human labour and to achieve cost-effective and large-scale data processing. Additionally, WP4 is utilising semantic technologies for the seamless interoperation between heterogeneous systems (recording, simulation and scenario catalogues) from different sources and using different meta-data formats. Semantic searching capabilities are expected to be provided, linked to graphical databases resources, focusing on scalability, query expansion and reasoning. Finally, synthetic scenarios based on variations of scenarios captured from real-world recordings are expected to be processed by SYNERGIES processing modules and pipelines. Scenario augmentation substantially increases the diversity and complexity of the data to be analysed, by constructing exponential (but relevant) data variations out of finite number of recordings, and by adding rare scenarios or integrating other traffic participants virtually that are not present in the original recordings.

- From TRL3 to TRL5

The KR continues to clarify specific aspects, as described below:

- WP4 - The semi-automated annotation system will be a cloud application that enables the execution of data processing pipelines, and the deployment of UIs for annotators to produce scene-level descriptions. ML techniques, like active learning, will be at the core of the system, to effectuate the automated part. Overall, an expectation of at least 50% of annotation time is expected, depending on the data complexity. Semantic technologies will be implemented as graph databases deployed in cloud applications, using SPARQL or other standard interfaces to multiply interoperability.
- WP5 - It is providing input and feedback to the development of the data processing tools such they are useful for the scenario methodology to be applied. In addition, WP5 will leverage the tools to enable efficient and effective scenario generation methods and tools.

3.2.1.5 KR5. Stakeholders buy-in through & promotion to standardisation

SYNERGIES is deploying the platform (WP7) and involving stakeholders to validate its usability and ensure buy-in (WP8). To do this, WP10 expects to train 100 users to facilitate the use of the platform and to create a pool of experts fostering the acceleration of CCAM validation in Europe. Additionally, SYNERGIES is working intensively to contribute to the creation of new standards and updates, especially of ISO/DIS 34504, ASAM, ISO/PAS 8800.

- From TRL2 to TRL6

The KR continues to clarify specific aspects, as described below:

- WP5 - It is contributing to standards regarding scenarios and scenario generation.
- WP7 - it delivers the SYNERGIES Platform and ensures its functionality and usability. WP7 works closely with stakeholders to validate the platform, ensuring it meets their needs (WP8). Additionally, WP7 collaborates with WP10 to train the users by creating a user handbook.
- WP8 - It is contributing to achieving KR5 by assessing the platform's usability and alignment with end-user needs. T8.2 plays a central role by implementing a feedback collection process—using forms or surveys—to identify potential barriers to adoption, enhance user satisfaction, and build trust. The insights gathered will be useful for identifying and prioritizing gaps and areas for improvement in the platform.

3.2.1.6 KR6. Governance tools

The governance tools support the qualified use of the scenario dataspace, e.g., for the selection of scenario-based test cases for safety assessment. Such scenario-based safety assessment can be part of procedures for type approval or certification given a prescribed ODD. The tools are aimed to provide metrics for the completeness of the scenario dataspace for the given ODD, and for the representativeness of the sample of scenarios for the ODD. Also, tools for quality checks to be performed when adding scenarios to an individual scenario database will be provided in WP6.

- From TRL 3 to TRL5

The KR continues to clarify specific aspects, as described below:

- WP5 - It is providing the scenario concept and other definitions regarding scenarios that will form the basis for analysing completeness and representativeness.
- WP6 - The objective of WP6 is to develop the governance tools.
- WP7 - WP7 supports this key focus by ensuring the integration and functionality of governance tools. WP7 ensures and verifies that the platform provides metrics for assessing the completeness and representativeness of the scenario dataspace for the given ODD.

3.2.2 Individual Key Results

A high-level description of the Individual exploitation plans has been described by the beneficiaries and associated partners during the proposal phase. Divided in five categories their ambitions are presented below. A complementary assessment has been realized to understand at individual level what are their exploitation plans and needs (Table 9).

- OEMs - Partners: BMW, PSA, REN, TME

The goal of the project is to build a sustainable, usable scenario database that covers a representative scenario space by using heterogeneous data sources and automated identification

of relevant scenarios. The collaborative, EU-wide approach and standardized interfaces enable maximum acceptance and minimum integration efforts.

- Tiers - Partners: FCE, SIE-NL, SIE-BE

Research results obtained from the project are expected to be integrated into the tool chain for testing automated vehicles, thus expanding their product portfolio. The results will also be used for engineering projects related to driving functions with automated vehicles together with OEMs. SYNERGIES project outcomes will be used to further develop internal processes on assessment and development of safety systems for CCAM. Furthermore, the developed SYNERGIES framework will help to develop (and sell) the safety systems with the largest impact on road safety. In addition, cooperation with OEMs, and official bodies will be improved based on a generally accepted dataspace, methods and tools for the completeness and representativity of scenarios.

- SMEs - Partners: IVEX, MOSAIC, VUFO

The project aims to further developing new key technologies, frameworks and software that accurately cover the needs of industrial partners, OEMs and Tiers. A close contact with the target users allows SMEs to target specific crucial points and to efficiently design solutions that perfectly fit the market needs.

- Non-industrial project partners: IDI, IDI_DE, CRF, AVL, CEESAR, CLEPA, CTAG, DLR, ERT, ICCS, RWTH, IRTSX, PAVE, RISE, TNO, TUE, UNIGE, VICOM, VIF

Non-industrial project partners are gaining know-how and expertise in the field of scenarios generation. Specifically, they are learning about the necessary tools, knowledge, and methodologies to optimize access to relevant, representative, and continuously updated scenarios. This knowledge will later be applied in future research and consultancy projects. All partners have a keen interest in participating in this project not only because it fits with their strategic individual plans but also, and mainly, because they foresee strong potential for the joint exploitation of the project results and the creation of sustainable collaboration in a win-win manner.

- Associated partners: TORC, SWRE, FEVIO, UoW

Associated partners will leverage the project's efforts and expertise to advance its core activities and focal priorities in the field. They are also identifying and developing new initiatives, platforms, or specialized forums to broaden the project's goals and achieve a wider adoption by the CCAM community. Several SYNERGIES partners are involved in the CCAM Partnership Executive Group, developing the Strategic Research & Innovation Agenda (SRIA) and the Horizon Europe Work Programmes for CCAM and will ensure that the usage of the tools and platform developed by SYNERGIES is encouraged in the new calls for proposals to maximize their uptake for future EU and national funded R&I activities in the field. Moreover, EUCAR, supporting SYNERGIES, offers the platform for exchange with all other OEMs who may be willing to join at a later stage the project, when specific scenario database governance and access mechanisms will be put in place.

Table 9 details the specific exploitation objectives of project partners, including any support or collaboration required to successfully achieve their exploitation plans. It can be noted that some partners have not identified up until now the support required, described as N/A. Partners have answered the following questions:

- Exploitation Objective - Regarding the SYNERGIES project, can you outline what your company's exploitation objective is when the project ends? Please describe the result to be achieved or the problem to be solved for your company by the end of the project.
- Support or collaboration needed - What support or collaboration do you need from the project consortium to effectively pursue your exploitation objective?

Project Partner	Exploitation Objective	Support or collaboration needed
AVL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High number of accessible scenarios • Maximised usability and coverage of scenarios • Use of heterogeneous and inclusive data sources for the generation of scenarios is enabled 	Data Providers, Tool Providers
BMW	A commonly agreed way of describing scenario implementations or an interoperability between different scenario implementations.	Constructive discussions on how to align the two mainly used scenario implementation formats ADScene and OSC XML.
CLEPA	CLEPA aims to disseminate the results and the platform to its members and its network.	Details, information and results.
TUE	Ground their AI research in requirements of the real-world applications and achieve some level of external validity of the techniques we develop.	Sharing domain expertise, datasets and/or simulators
ERT	<p>New knowledge and know-how to understand better how European stakeholders can be benefited from the results of the project.</p> <p>Design policies</p>	Collaboration from project partners
FCE	Cost reduction, synergies between platform of development and platform of validation,	Defining a holistic view about the validation pipeline globally and define what is mandatory or not to perform.

Project Partner	Exploitation Objective	Support or collaboration needed
DLR	<p>DLR goal is to improve its existing methods for scenario-based development, connect research prototypes with industrial tools, and strengthen the alignment of its research with industry needs.</p> <p>DLR's main exploitation objective is to use the results of the project to enhance its simulations tools. The ability to access a reliable and comprehensive scenario database for use in simulation, especially in conjunction with the OSTAR toolchain. Reducing the effort and costs to obtain scenario data for testing and validation of CCAM systems.</p> <p>The expectation is that this scenario marketplace is self-enriching in the future and is scalable for future needs.</p>	<p>Insight to current problems, challenges, and use-cases; opportunities for collaborative research.</p> <p>Providing interfaces to the SYNERGIES platform to adapt our OSTAR simulation tool.</p>
IDI	<p>Give their customers the most up to date services for homologation and development of ADAS and ADS systems.</p>	N/A
IRTSYSX	<p>Use the available interoperability assets, tools and scenario databases produced, to continue research activities on CCAM validation.</p>	N/A
MOSAIC	<p>Gain experience in data trustworthiness requirements, definition of trust metrics and research on future requirements for data quality. Development of a methodology for data quality assessment. Development of a tool for inspection of AI-driven data.</p> <p>Development of a tool for assessment and evaluation of a certain scenario applied in other areas or countries.</p> <p>Gain experience in the definition, integration, test, validation and improvement of the scenario's platform.</p>	N/A

Project Partner	Exploitation Objective	Support or collaboration needed
PAVE	Communicate about it, engage with relevant stakeholders, including the public, and develop training programmes.	Provide content, methodologies for training and communication
REN	Provide standards over the whole data & scenario process to exchange and share data & scenarios. Create interoperability between scenario databases Produce an overarching SCDB frame working interconnecting the SCDB and giving access to them.	N/A
RISE	Help industrial partners make use of the results, make own use of the dataspace for future research.	Accessible and to-the-point information on how to use the results
RWTH	RWTH wants to extend our knowledge and tooling about scenario identification, scenario extraction, scenario enrichment and especially scenario generation to improve and ease the usage of scenarios for application for testing automated vehicles. RWTH wants to exploit this knowledge and tooling in upcoming research activities and projects and contribute to a widely accepted and available scenario methodology for testing automated vehicles. Furthermore, RWTH wants to exploit the knowledge and tooling by assisting industry partners in consultancy projects to enable harmonization in this field.	RWTH needs to find a common ground for the scenario methodology (especially, but not limited to, scenario generation) and related concepts to effectively pursue the exploitation plan and contribute to harmonization in the scenario-based testing of automated vehicles.
SIE	Use scenarios in their projects, and increase the ease of simulations at customers, thus increasing the use of simulation in general and the use of our product more specifically.	N/A
PSA	Exploit the ADSCENE data base in the SYNERGIES scenario framework	SYNERGIES partnership is consistent with goals

Project Partner	Exploitation Objective	Support or collaboration needed
SWRe	The main goal is to contribute to the development of the CCAM field from a risk and safety relevant point of view	N/A
TNO	Quantification metric for representativeness of sets of scenarios for specific ODDs, interoperability of scenario databases in a worthwhile business case.	Effective collaboration on WP6
TORC	TORC wants to bring a safe L4 system on the road in the US.	Shareable scenario library
TME	TME will need to follow the requirements for safety assessment by third party, either for type approval (regulators) or for consumer assessment organisations. TME would ideally need a clear process including the needs such as data that are or will be required. Also, it would like to understand what possibilities are to use own data available internally to be applied to the defined safety assurance framework in the project and eventually the data framework	TME needs are not personalised, they relate to all industry partners, so I encourage not to only engage with single industry players but rather with the industry community or representatives.
UNIGE	UNIGE aims to publish high-quality research papers in reputable scientific journals and conferences to disseminate our findings from the SYNERGIES project, which focuses on applying machine learning to synthetic scenario generation and automatic scenario detection. Additionally, UNIGE would like to develop the testing platform to ensure it is flexible and reusable in other contexts as well.	UNIGE would like the consortium to be open to collaboration to produce scientific publications together.
UoW	As a database (DB) owner, UoW primary objective is to ensure that our database meets industry standards and regulatory requirements, making it more attractive and useful for new and existing users across various sectors.	N/A

Project Partner	Exploitation Objective	Support or collaboration needed
VUFO	From VUFO's point of view, SYNERGIES marketplace would be very useful for filtering GIDAS-PCM scenarios and making them available to various stakeholders for a fee.	A usable SYNERGIES platform with connection to the necessary data.
VICOM	As a non-for-profit research organisation, VICOM seeks to enhance its knowledge, to have more opportunities to continue doing applied research	Participate in tasks where VICOM learns from industrial requirements, and coordinate with technical partners to advance our expertise
VIF	New knowledge and models, new methods, frameworks, solutions and tools opening new markets aimed at improving the development, training, virtual testing, and validation of CCAM systems. Proven know-how and expertise in the field of scenarios generation. Optimized access to relevant, representative, and continuously updated scenarios. Knowledge will be applied in future research and consultancy projects.	Collection of scenarios, creation of the dataspace.

Table 9. Individual Exploitation Plans - Initial Assessment

3.3 Exploitation Plan

The exploitation plan consolidates aspects, ranging from the specialized support of the European Commission to their exploitation, dissemination and standardization platforms, with the cooperation of identified entities and standardization bodies, including CCAM European funded projects, and the expert's network platform sustained by WP9. Each one of them aligned with project milestones to support each phase of the project. As SYNERGIES project is at an early stage, invitations to collaborate need to be planned accordingly.

3.3.1 European Services Support

The European commission supports the following two initiatives, aimed to provide services to EU-funded projects.

- **Booster [21]:** A free-of-charge service that provides personalized support to boost dissemination and exploitation. Supported by both, project officer and coordinator, SYNERGIES project has applied to the service. The plan is to continue the process in M14 due to aspects related to business models require to be clarified.
- **Horizon Standardisation Booster [22]:** A new EU Standardisation service that supports European funded projects in standardisation aspects. HSBooster.eu has been already

contacted to discuss how to collaborate. The plan is to understand how to use their expertise and knowledge to potentially adapt KRs to facilitate the process of standardization.

3.3.2 Entities

With regards to entities, the exploitation started promoting the project and looking ways to collaborate exchanging experiences, knowledge, and potential data. The discussion started with representatives of the entity described below:

- Data for Road Safety ecosystem (DFRS) - it has been performed an initial high-level discussion on a potential collaboration. From the SYNERGIES project side, the proposal is the involvement of the DFRS as an early adopter of the platform to test it. There is an open possibility for them to use their data to recreate scenarios of their interest. It is planned to continue the discussions in M16 since milestone 8 will be achieved at that point of the project (Table 11).

3.3.3 EU Funded Projects

With regards to EU-funded projects, there are two activities planned:

- The first one involves an invitation to maximum five related CCAM funded projects to collaborate in a collective exploitation approach. The proposal suggests that other projects utilize or test a selected KR that is beneficial to each project's scope. This considering that like SYNERGIES, there are combined eighteen projects ending between 2026 and 2027 (Table 8). Once a detailed analysis of those projects is realized, the proposal is expected to be discussed internally with the steering committee.
- The second activity involves collaborating to the exchange of new knowledge, experiences, and recommendations from projects related to scenarios, testing and validation of CCAM. From the exploitation side, the one project already contacted is described below:

PODIUM Project [23] - In relation to the lessons, experiences and challenges obtained during their testing of the real-life scenarios. Podium is evaluating 5 use cases at urban and inter-urban level. In November 2024 during the PODIUM Review meeting, it has been presented SYNERGIES project. The plan is to perform a workshop in month 9 to support the milestone 6 (see Table 11).

3.3.4 Stakeholders Engagement

Discussions, workshops and surveys require to be coordinated with the WP9, to take advantage of the SYNERGIES expert's network platform. This strategy is essential to obtain feedback and to raise the interest of external stakeholders about the KRs. There are about 240 experts participating in the SUNRISE expert's platform to be invited to participate in SYNERGIES project. Table 10 presents the current organizations involved, divided by stakeholder's category. Their involvement is expected at different stages of the project.

Additionally, the exploitation board, which goal is to provide advice in relation to the project exploitation plans, is expected to be defined from the organisations listed below:

Stakeholder Category	Organizations
OEMs	Audi, BMW, CRF, Daimler, EasyMile, Ford Otosan, Einride, Honda, IVECO, NIO, Nissan, OTOKAR, Renault, Toyota Motor Corporation, Volvo Car Corporation, Volkswagen, Volvo Autonomous Solutions, Zoox.
TIERs	Aptiv, Aurota, AVL Bosch, Denso, Ericsson, GMV, Magna, Mobileye, NTT Data, NXP, Sensirion, Swift Navigation, ALEIA, VALEO, Veoneer, Zenseact, ZF, FEV.
Research	AIT, CARTELL, CERTH/HIT, CETRAN, Chalmers, CIDAUT, DFKI, DLR, Fraunhofer IESE, JARI, KIT, TUBS, VTI, VTT, Trinity College Dublin, Technische Hochschule Ingolstadt.
Road Operator	ASFINAG, ERF, Globalvia.
Consumer organisation	ADAC, AstaZero, Euro NCAP, IRU, OAMTC, TÜV Rheinland, TÜV Süd
Public Authority	BASSt, Helmond City, DGT, ENISA, JRC, Helmond City, Luxembourg Ministry of Economy, RDW, Rijkswaterstaat, Red Sea Global, Swedish Transport Administration, THI, TRB (US), UC Berkeley (US), UK DoT, VIAS Belgium.
Association	5GAA, ACEA, AutomotiveNL, AVSC, BasqueCCAM, CLEPA, CORTE, Car2Car consortium, EUCAR, SOGEI, UITP.
Standardisation and Regulation	ASAM, ETSI, SAE, ISO, UNECE.
Service/Technology Provider	ATOS, Autobotik, Foretellix, MAPtm, NVIDIA, PTV, Sony, Telespazio, UTAC.

Table 10. SUNRISE Experts Network Transferred to SYNERGIES Project

Considering the evolution of the project, the exploitation plan has been aligned with the milestones to be achieved. This synchronization is expected to contribute with better detail to the users' needs, in relation to the topics covered by the project. The plan involves the external obtention of inputs and feedback to be used internally by WP leaders, complemented by a detailed identification of interested stakeholders in the testing and long-term usage of the KR. The exploitation plan detailed in Table 11 requires to be discussed with the steering committee to understand the feasibility of the activities planned. This verification is expected specifically with WP9 which leads the stakeholder engagement strategy.

No.	Milestone name	Related WP	Date	Collaboration plan with identified entities and EU Funded projects (Section 3.1.1)
1	Project kick-off	WP1	M1	Finalized

No.	Milestone name	Related WP	Date	Collaboration plan with identified entities and EU Funded projects (Section 3.1.1)
2	Risk and quality procedures	WP1	M3	Finalized
3	First release of data interoperability requirements	WP2	M6	Finalized
4	Methodology for data quality assessment	WP3	M6	Finalized
5	Preliminary report of data available from external sources	WP3	M8	Open data will be requested to: - 2 Entity - 2 EU funded projects
6	Preliminary scenario methodology	WP5	M10	- Identify and invite 2 EU funded projects related to scenarios testing, simulation or deployment to provide knowledge and key lessons obtained. - Organize 1 workshop
7	First release of data available processed	WP4	M12	It is not foreseeing any contribution
8	First release of data generated from vehicles, roadside infrastructure, and drones, advances simulation tools and synthetic data based on Generative AI	WP3	M16	Promotion of the milestone with public and private entities in the CCAM/ITS domain. - 1 exploitation feedback session/workshop
9	First set of scenarios generated	WP5	M16	Promotion of the milestone to public and private entities in the CCAM/ITS domain
10	First interoperability report	WP5	M18	It is not foreseeing any contribution
11	Training material for the 1 st Platform release	WP7, WP10	M18	It is not foreseeing any contribution
12	1 st Platform release	WP7	M18	Internal test of the platform
13	Mid-term project report	WP1	M18	It is not foreseeing any contribution
14	Feedback from users received from the 1 st release	WP8	M20	Invitation to test the platform - 1 entity - 2 EU funded projects

No.	Milestone name	Related WP	Date	Collaboration plan with identified entities and EU Funded projects (Section 3.1.1)
15	Second release of data available and generated processed	WP4	M20	It is not foreseeing any contribution
16	Second set of scenarios generated	WP5	M22	- 1 exploitation feedback session/workshop
17	First set of tools available	WP4, WP5, WP6	M22	Promotion of the milestone to public and private entities in the CCAM/ITS domain
18	Training material for the 2 nd Platform release	WP7, WP10	M24	It is not foreseeing any contribution
19	2 nd Platform release	WP7	M24	It is not foreseeing any contribution
20	Feedback from users received from the 2 nd release	WP8	M26	Promotion of the milestone with public and private entities in the CCAM/ITS domain. - 1 exploitation feedback session/workshop with multiple entities and EU funded project representatives
21	All tools available	WP4, WP5, WP6	M34	Invitation to test the platform - 1 entity - 1 EU funded project
22	Training material for the 3 rd Platform release	WP7, WP10	M36	It is not foreseeing any contribution
23	Platform final release	WP7	M36	- 1 exploitation feedback session/workshop involving participants of the expert's network
24	Final Event organised	WP1, WP10	M36	D1.6 Final Exploitation Plan

Table 11. Exploitation Plan Aligned with Project Milestones

4 CONCLUSIONS

The interest from industry, public and research entities towards the KRs of the SYNERGIES project varies depending on the stakeholder (e.g., European Commission, OEMs, insurance companies, associations, government agencies, public entities, etc.). As described in section 3.1.1 Broad Opportunities for Leveraging Key Results, there are different possibilities of exploitation at European, national and local level. KRs address stakeholders needs covering a variety of fields. Additionally, the Targeted Entities and Strategic Collaborations proposed in Section 3.1.2 extend the possibilities of a successful exploitation. However, what is required is the balancing of the versatility of the KRs, the stakeholders need, and the project resources to produce solutions mature enough to continue to be used, sustained, and maintained in the long-term. Therefore, once the prototypes of the KRs are produced, this approach requires further discussions with European Commission representatives, CCAM associations and partnerships, national and local authorities and homologation entities regarding their needs. Nevertheless, the combined exploitation strategy with other EU-funded projects offers an opportunity to expand the boundaries of innovation and collaboration through European funds. It is required to clarify internally if this exploitation goal can be pursued, analysing the risks and the projects that could be involved.

The designed exploitation plan aims to have a clear vision on the activities to be realized along the project, as well as to overcome potential challenges that can emerge. Internally, a collaboration within all the WPs is expected, especially WP9 in relation to the stakeholder's engagement and involvement. Externally, an active promotion of the achievements and KRs evolution is required, to raise the interest of stakeholders. The exploitation plan requires to be further developed and discussed with the Steering Committee and project partners.

From WP9 and the SYNERGIES expert's network, it is required to appoint the members of the Exploitation Board. These will be selected members of the expert's network, representing key exploitation stakeholders to be invited to join an Exploitation Board supporting the work of the Innovation & Exploitation Manager (I&EM) in Task 1.3. The Exploitation Board will also contribute, to boost the opportunities of exploitation of the KRs, with the support obtained from the exploitation, dissemination and standardization platforms and from the European Commission as mentioned in Section 3.3.1

The KRs, and specifically the CCAM scenario-based simulation testing, proposed by the project require to be promoted as a complementary solution to field trials and demonstrations to ensure a more efficient use of resources and efforts to enable the analysis of multiple variables before real-life testing. The KRs ensure an accurate planning and provide a visual context, helpful for the request of authorizations in the case roads need to be close for testing for example.

Along with the initial descriptions of individual exploitations addressed to, the KRs to design solutions to OEMs, internal discussions have included the perspectives and needs of other stakeholders of the CCAM landscape. Additionally, the SYNERGIES platform is expected to support data from external users. These exploitation opportunities need to be seized due to multiple users and data robustness so that they can improve the quality and accuracy of the designed scenarios.

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A. APPENDIX A

Detailed evaluation of the CCAM projects.

CCAM Projects	Connection with SYNERGIES and Potential Interest
<p>Project#1</p> <p>Project acronym UNLOCK-CEI</p> <p>Title Unlocking the Cloud Edge IoT demand potential in Europe</p> <p>Teaser UNLOCK CEI's ambition is to UNLOCK the potential for accelerating the deployment of the Cloud-to-Edge-IoT (CEI) computing continuum in Europe by focusing on the demand-side drivers and challenges to identify technology-driven innovation and business opportunities driving...</p> <p>URL https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101070571</p> <p>Project end date 30/11/2024</p>	<p>In general, the UNLOCK-CEI project evaluates data processing and analytics close where the data is generated using Cloud-to-Edge-IoT (CEI) computing continuum. An important aspect for CCAM operators, however, not relevant for the SYNERGIES project as is more focused on the recreation of CCAM scenarios for testing and validation. The UNLOCK-CEI project approach can be applicable once developed the SYNERGIES platform.</p>
<p>Project #2</p> <p>Project acronym Move2CCAM</p> <p>Title MethODs and tools for comprehensive impact Assessment of the CCAM solutions for passengers and goods</p> <p>Teaser Mobility is crossing a new digital frontier in terms of connectivity, allowing vehicles to communicate to each other, to the infrastructure and to other transport systems users. However, the potential implications and impacts of integration of CCAM solutions into the mobility...</p> <p>URL https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069852</p> <p>Project end date 28/02/2025</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CCAM Scenarios and use cases: Descriptions of the pilots and experiences of real-world autonomous vehicle trials. - Data: The roadmap of the data and data collection tools. - Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)
<p>Project #3</p> <p>Project acronym SELFY</p> <p>Title SELF assessment, protection & healing tools for a trustworthy and resilient CCAM</p> <p>Teaser</p>	<p>SELFY project focuses on the data protection which is not the focus of SYNERGIES project. Therefore, it is a secondary aspect that can be analysed afterwards by SYNERGIES partners.</p>

SELFY will increase CCAM ecosystem's safety, security, robustness, and resilience by researching and developing a toolbox made of collaborative tools which main pillars are: (i) situational awareness, through collaborative perception and monitoring; (ii) data sharing...	
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069748	
Project end date	
31/05/2025	
Project #4	
Project acronym	
FAME	
Title	
Framework for coordination of Automated Mobility in Europe	
Teaser	
FAME will develop and validate common methodologies and tools to facilitate the sharing of best practices and lessons learned to support the collaboration within the community of CCAM stakeholders across the complex cross-sectorial value chain needed for the organisation and...	- Methodologies: The universal framework for road testing designed by FAME project can be used to adapt the SYNERGIES platform to the testing of real-life scenarios.
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069898	
Project end date	
30/06/2025	
Project #5	
Project acronym	
CONNECT	
Title	
Continuous and Efficient Cooperative Trust Management for Resilient CCAM	
Teaser	
"CONNECT addresses the convergence of security and safety in CCAM by assessing dynamic trust relationships and defining a trust reasoning framework based on which involved entities can establish trust for cooperatively executing safety-critical functions. This will enable both...	
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069688	
Project end date	
31/08/2025	
Project #6	
Project acronym	
EVENTS	
Title	
	-CCAM scenarios and use cases: Explore the results obtained from the evaluated use cases, and the data process:

Reliable in-Vehicle perception and decision-making in complex environmental conditions	a) Interaction with VRUs, b) Non-Standard and Unstructured Road Conditions
Teaser	c) Low Visibility and Adverse Weather Conditions.
Driving is a challenging task. In our everyday life as drivers, we are facing unexpected situations we need to handle in a safe and efficient way. The same is valid for Connected and Automated Vehicles (CAVs), which also need to handle these situations, to a certain extent...	Unexpected situations in different environments.
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069614	
Project end date	
31/08/2025	
Project #7	
Project acronym	
SUNRISE	
Title	
Safety assurance framework for connected, automated mobility Systems	
Teaser	-Methodologies: Use the lessons learned by the project in the development of the Safety Assurance Framework. Consider also the expert's network to obtain feedback on the design of the SYNERGIES platform, methodologies and standards.
Safety assurance of Cooperative, Connected, and Automated Mobility (CCAM) technologies and systems is a crucial factor for their successful adoption in society, yet it remains to be a significant challenge. CCAM must prove to be safe and reliable in every...	
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069573	
Project end date	
31/08/2025	
Project #8	
Project acronym	
SINFONICA	
Title	
Social Innovation to Foster Inclusive Cooperative, connected and Automated mobility	-User needs: Through SINFONICA project understand how to engage CCAM providers, operators, transport operators, public administrations, service providers.
Teaser	-CCAM Scenarios and use cases: recommendations for CCAM large scale demonstrators.
SINFONICA aims to develop functional, efficient, and innovative strategies, methods and tools to engage CCAM users, providers and other stakeholders (i.e. citizens, including vulnerable users, transport operators, public administrations, service providers, researchers, vehicle...	Other topics that can be used include:
URL	- CCAM vocabulary and stakeholders needs and requirements for CCAM solutions
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101064988	- Understanding the Gap of CCAM solutions deployment
Project end date	
31/08/2025	
Project #9	
Project acronym	

i4Driving	
Title	
Integrated 4D driver modelling under uncertainty	
Teaser	
The vision of i4Driving is to lay the foundation for a new industry-standard methodology to establish a credible and realistic human road safety baseline for virtual assessment of CCAM systems. The two central ideas we propose are (1) a multi-level, modular and extendable...	-Simulation: Analyse how to use the lessons learnt from the simulation library -Methodologies: to account for the uncertainty in both human behaviour and use cases CCAM Scenarios and use case: - Methodology and results: relevant use cases and safety-critical scenarios - Evaluation criteria and detailed description of field experiments - Harmonized, annotated, and processed data in usable format
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101076165	
Project end date	
30/09/2025	
Project #10	
Project acronym	
V4SAFETY	
Title	
Vehicles and VRU Virtual eValuation of Road Safety	
Teaser	
In order to set policies for road safety in the coming decades and push for Vision Zero, an accepted and reliable method for the comparison of safety measures for CCAM is needed. The proposed method will deal with the safety of all road users, from vulnerable road users to...	-Methodologies: Analyse the developed framework for the evaluation and comparison of safety measures for CCAM. -Standards: Understand how the V4SAFETY project set policies for road safety.
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101075068	
Project end date	
30/09/2025	
Project #11	
Project acronym	
PoDIUM	
Title	
PDI connectivity and cooperation enablers building trust and sustainability for CCAM	
Teaser	
In PoDIUM, using and enhancing the facilities of 3 well-equipped Living Labs in Germany, Italy and Spain we define a rich set of demanding CCAM UCs to identify and assess all the connectivity and cooperation enablers and needs that will allow the proposed higher levels of...	-CCAM Scenarios and use cases: Analyse the CCAM services designed, the use cases and the interoperability aspects to consider when testing automated vehicles in different environments. PODIUM project uses road infrastructure, communication network components and vehicle sensors to the testing of CCAM services. Living labs in Germany, Italy and Spain, in urban, highway and cross-border environments.
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069547	
Project end date	
30/09/2025	
Project #12	
Project acronym	

IN2CCAM	<p>CCAM scenarios and use cases: In the D2.3 Use Case Definition, the project presents living labs in Tampere, Trikala, Turin, Vigo, Bari and Quadrilatero. Use cases definition . Explore the lessons learned in the use cases definition or scenarios in the living labs.</p> <p>Standards: Analyse their interoperability framework and open standards - Their Study questions and KPIs of CCAM ecosystem is another aspect that can be beneficial to SYNERGIES</p>
Title	
Enhancing Integration and Interoperability of CCAM eco-system (IN2CCAM)	
Teaser	
IN2CCAM consortium, according to the vision of Horizon Europe framework programme from 2021-2027 that aims to accelerate the implementation of innovative CCAM technologies and systems for passengers and goods, intends develop, implement and demonstrate innovative services for...	
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101076791	
Project end date	
31/10/2025	
Project #13	
Project acronym	
AWARE2ALL	
Title	<p>-CCAM scenarios and use cases: Critical accident scenarios and high-level requirements</p> <p>-Methodologies: The experiences gained through the Safety framework for considering Human Machine Interaction can contribute to SYNERGIES.</p>
Safety systems and human-machine interfaces oriented to diverse population towards future scenarios with increasing share of highly automated vehicles	
Teaser	
Facing to the challenge of future highly automated vehicles, where occupants can freely orient themselves to engage in non-driving activities. This new environment prompts questions about how car occupants will sit, what activities they will engage in, and how they...	
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101076868	
Project end date	
31/10/2025	
Project #14	
Project acronym	
Althena	
Title	<p>-CCAM scenarios and use cases: Report on initial use case evaluation</p> <p>-Data: Lessons from data (real/synthetic data management), models (data fusion, hybrid AI approaches), and testing (physical/virtual XiL set-ups with scalable MLOps).</p>
AI-based CCAM: Trustworthy, Explainable, and Accountable	
Teaser	
Connected and Cooperative Automotive Mobility (CCAM) solutions have emerged thanks to novel Artificial Intelligence (AI) which can be trained with huge amounts of data to produce driving functions with better-than-human performance under certain conditions. The race on AI...	
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101076754	
Project end date	

31/10/2025	
Project #15	
Project acronym	
CONDUCTOR	
Title	
Fleet and traffic management systems for conducting future cooperative mobility	
Teaser	
The CONDUCTOR project's main goal is to design, integrate and demonstrate advanced, high-level traffic and fleet management that will allow efficient and globally optimal transport of passengers and goods, while ensuring seamless multi-modality and interoperability...	-Simulation: Simulation models and tools empowered by machine learning and data fusion.
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101077049	
Project end date	
31/10/2025	
Project #16	
Project acronym	
MAIA	
Title	
Multimodal Access for Intelligent Airports	
Teaser	
MAIA's vision is that, within 5-10 years, CCAM and UAM based services will be available in an integrated manner with the airport infrastructure and the remaining access modes. AI tools and digital twins will be used for anticipating the impacts of different service...	-CCAM scenarios and use cases: Experiences of this project can be used to extend the scenarios and use cases to airport infrastructure and the remaining access modes.
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101114853	
Project end date	
30/11/2025	
Project #17	
Project acronym	
AI4CCAM	
Title	
Trustworthy AI for CCAM	
Teaser	
Considering Artificial Intelligence (AI) capabilities and potential risks, and considering its limitations, AI4CCAM will develop an open environment for integrating trustworthy-by-design AI models of vulnerable road user behaviour anticipation in urban traffic...	-Simulation: Simulation scenarios of road users interacting with automated vehicles in three use cases.
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101076911	
Project end date	

31/12/2025	
Project #18	
Project acronym	
AUGMENTED CCAM	
Title	
Augmenting and Evaluating the Physical and Digital Infrastructure for CCAM deployment	
Teaser	
AUGMENTED CCAM aims to understand, harmonise and evaluate in an augmented manner adapted and novel support solutions of Physical, Digital and Communication (PDI) infrastructure, to advance its readiness for large scale deployment of CCAM solutions for all. The project will...	-CCAM Scenarios and use cases: Large-scale use cases operation of CCAM solutions for all actors. Seven (7) test sites across three (3) European Countries (France, Latvia, Spain), encompassing a vast spectrum of physical (living labs, closed areas, open traffic highway, urban and peri-urban/rural environments) and virtual (DT, AV & driving simulators) test beds. - Digital Twins for CCAM Applications - The Case of Augmented CCAM and Beyond
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069717	
Project end date	
31/12/2025	
Project #19	
Project acronym	
MODI	
Title	
A leap towards SAE L4 automated driving features	
Teaser	
The introduction of Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM) can make a significant improvement to logistic chains. The MODI project will identify and largely resolve barriers on confined areas and on public roads for SAE L4 CCAM vehicles on the corridor from...	-CCAM Scenarios and use cases: Use cases in logistic vehicle operations. Five different use cases, each describing a part of the logistics chain. Analysing confined areas and on public roads on the corridor from Rotterdam to Oslo.
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101076810	
Project end date	
31/03/2026	
Project #20	
Project acronym	
SETO	
Title	
Smart Enforcement of Transport Operations	
Teaser	
"SETO will deliver an innovative digital solution that will allow authorities to access all information required for the smart enforcement of transport and safety legislation in real-time using the 'one-click' principle. This will address the significant challenge of..."	-Standards: Experiences in relation to how authorities access all information required for the smart enforcement of transport and safety legislation in real-time using the 'one-click' principle. - Engagement: Understand also how the project fosters the collective intelligence of all stakeholders to build a viable system based on ""incentives"" rather than forcing its adoption."
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101103695	
Project end date	

31/05/2026	
Project #21	
Project acronym	
KEYSTONE	
Title	
knowledgeable comprehensive and fully integrated smart solution for resilient, sustainable and optimized transport operations	
Teaser	-Data exchange: Standardised APIs for data and information sharing between transport enforcement authorities and logistics operators based on a federated approach. Digital ecosystem framework
The overarching goal of KEYSTONE is to support the development of a sustainable, efficient, and safe transport system, allowing enforcement authorities to access data for the purpose of checking compliance with rules applied in the transport of goods and passengers. The aim...	
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101103740	
Project end date	
31/05/2026	
Project #22	
Project acronym	
CCAM-ERAS	
Title	
CCAM-Employment Realization through the Acquisition of Skills (CCAM-ERAS)	
Teaser	This project addresses issues on the CCAM labour market and skills which is not relevant for SYNERGIES project.
CCAM-ERAS aims to build towards the future and address the transition to connected, cooperative and automated mobility (CCAM) from a socio-economic perspective. The project will develop the necessary knowledge and prepare for the possibilities that potentially will arise from...	
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101147129	
Project end date	
31/07/2026	
Project #23	
Project acronym	
ROADVIEW	
Title	
Robust Automated Driving in Extreme Weather	
Teaser	-CCAM Scenarios and use cases: Under Complex environment and traffic conditions.
Complex environment and traffic conditions have major impact on the safety and operations of Connected and Automated Vehicles (CAVs). Weather affects not only the vehicle performance but also the roadway infrastructure, thereby increases the risk of collision and traffic...	
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069576	

Project end date	
31/08/2026	
Project #24	
Project acronym	
ULTIMO	
Title	
ULTIMO - Advancing Sustainable User-centric Mobility with Automated Vehicles	
Teaser	
During the past few years many projects and entities were undertaken deploying and testing Automated Vehicles (AVs) for public transportation and logistics. However, despite their ambition, all these projects stayed on the level of elaborated experimentation and...	-CCAM scenarios and use cases: Experiences from the three sites in Europe 15 or more multi-vendor SAE L4 AVs per site.
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101077587	
Project end date	
30/09/2026	
Project #25	
Project acronym	
BERTHA	
Title	
BEhavioural ReplicaTion of Human drivers for CCAM	
Teaser	
Europe must seize the opportunities presented by connected, cooperative, and automated mobility (CCAM). For its deployment, powerful tools enabling the design and analysis of CCAM components, digitally and with a common language between TIERS an OEMs are needed. The lack of a...	-CCAM scenarios and use cases: automated driving functions into mixed traffic scenarios. This project focuses on TIERS and OEMs.
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101076360	
Project end date	
31/10/2026	
Project #26	
Project acronym	
AutoTRUST	
Title	
Autonomous self-adaptive services for TRansformational personalized inclUsiveness and resilience in mobiliTy	
Teaser	
The AutoTRUST project aims to develop and demonstrate a novel AI-leveraged self-adaptive framework of advanced vehicle technologies and solutions which optimize usability, perception, and experience on-board, and when boarding/off-boarding, in terms of security, privacy...	- CCAM scenarios and use cases: interaction between users and new automated modes of road transport and mobility services in the transition from human-driven to automated vehicles -Standards

URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101148123	
Project end date	
30/04/2027	
Project #27	
Project acronym	
EvoRoads	
Title	
Evolutionary Solutions for Realising a Holistic Safe System Approach for All Road Users	
Teaser	
The successful implementation of EU's 2021-2030 road safety policy is a milestone towards the target of zero fatalities in road transport by 2050 and requires a clear understanding of criteria that influence safety performance, development of solutions that promote safety...	
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101147850	
Project end date	
30/04/2027	
Project #28	
Project acronym	
CulturalRoad	
Title	
Cocreate, Embrace	
Teaser	
CulturalRoad develops sustainable and population - wide accepted deployment plans for Cooperative, Connected, and Autonomous Mobility (CCAM) services by combining participatory planning with a novel Five-Pointed Star Rating system able to capture both cultural and geographical...	
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101147397	
Project end date	
30/04/2027	
Project #29	
Project acronym	
FRODDO	
Title	
Federated cybeR-physical infrastructure for ODD cOntinuity	
Teaser	
	-Methodologies: Innovative models, tools, and services to revolutionise safety assessment frameworks - Defining safety criteria and quantification methodologies, EvoRoads covers the entire spectrum of the Safe System approach, which aims to eliminate fatalities and serious injuries on roadways. -Platform: The project features advanced AI-driven analytics, a connectivity platform, and low-cost smart signs. EvoRoads promises transformative impacts. Validation across seven locations in Europe,
	User needs: Societal acceptance of CCAM systems: The project uses a Five-Pointed Star Rating system to assess cultural and geographical diversity. It emphasises active engagement with local communities to gather insights on their mobility needs
	-CCAM Scenarios and use cases: Design ODDs that safely cooperate with Public Digital Infrastructure, incorporating feedback from authorities and operators. -Datasets

<p>The operational context is the cornerstone to ensure performance and safety of CCAM. The ODD, by design, defines the operating environment for which a system is designed for. On the other hand, Authorities and Road Operators are responsible for operating the PDI with a variety...</p>	
<p>URL https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101147819</p>	
<p>Project end date 31/05/2027</p>	
<p>Project #30</p>	
<p>Project acronym AUTOMOTIF</p>	
<p>Title Automation Towards Multimodal Transportation and Integration of Freight</p>	
<p>Teaser AutoMoTIF will focus on the development of strategies, business and governance models, regulatory recommendations and synergies that will enable the integration and interoperability of automated transport systems and solutions towards the operational automation of multimodal..</p>	<p>-CCAM Scenarios and use cases: focus on real challenges and gaps in seamless automated logistics that will be simulated in real settings and different geographical locations.</p>
<p>URL https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101147693</p>	
<p>Project end date 31/05/2027</p>	
<p>Project #31</p>	
<p>Project acronym Diversify - CCAM</p>	
<p>Title Diversify CCAM by integrating the European cultural and regional variations in the design and implementation of citizen-friendly systems to foster mobility equity</p>	
<p>Teaser CCAM solutions face a significant challenge characterized by decreased societal demand due to their difficulty in effectively conveying their advantages within existing mobility systems and adapting to the diverse environments where citizens live, work, and conduct their daily...</p>	<p>-CCAM scenarios and use cases: 12 pilot sites in six EU countries, examining differences in CCAM implementation between rural and urban environments, identifying barriers to the acceptance and efficiency of CCAM in these areas, and integrating cultural, geographical, and policy considerations into the design and development process. -Platform: The CCAM diversification tool and observatory.</p>
<p>URL https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101147484</p>	
<p>Project end date 31/05/2027</p>	
<p>Project #32</p>	
<p>Project acronym iDriving</p>	
<p>Title</p>	<p>-CCAM scenarios and use cases: TRL 6 prototype based on seven key pillars, all designed to work synergistically to</p>

iDriving - Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies	
Teaser	create an interactive, accurate and efficient solution to improve infrastructure safety of urban and secondary rural roads.
iDriving aims to deliver a TRL 6 prototype based on seven key pillars, all designed to work synergistically to create an interactive, accurate and efficient solution to improve infrastructure safety of urban and secondary rural roads. (i) A Safety Criteria Catalogue (SCC) for...	
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101147004	
Project end date	
30/06/2027	
Project #33	
Project acronym	-Data space: data creation methods through data compression, filtering and normalization will be developed, to allow efficient and greener storage in a data-oriented future
PLIADES	- Data sharing: through novel AI-based brokers and connectors using extended metadata, shaped through the project's best practices and domain expert's knowledge
Title	- Cross-domain AI connectors: active data discovery services through cross domain AI connectors will allow creating linked data spaces, enabling interoperability between previously disconnected entities, while data quality assessment services will facilitate real time data evaluation.
AI-Enabled Data Lifecycles Optimization and Data Spaces Integration for Increased Efficiency and Interoperability	
Teaser	
PLIADES advances the SoA dataspace reference architectures, towards a step change on the use of data as key enabler of technological advances in AI and Robotics. To this end, PLIADES research into novel, AI-enabled tools to advance full data life cycles integration, both...	
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101135988	
Project end date	
30/06/2027	
Project #34	
Project acronym	
OptiPEX	
Title	
Optimizing Passenger Experience in Public Transport	
Teaser	-CCAM Scenarios and use cases: cutting-edge measurement, analytics and interaction technologies to tailor services for specific user groups like wheelchair users and tourists.
The current global climate crisis and ongoing shift towards autonomous transport necessitate sustainable and passenger-centric public transport solutions. The goal of OptiPEX is to enhance of sense of comfort and safety of the passengers as well as the security and ease of...	Three living labs
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101146513	
Project end date	
31/10/2027	
Project #35	

Project acronym	
metaCCAZE	
Title	
Flexibly adapted MetaInnovations, use cases, collaborative business and governance models to accelerate deployment of smart and shared Zero Emission mobility for passengers and freight	-CCAM scenarios and use cases: Passenger and freight services (public transport, on-demand minibuses, bike sharing, deliveries) and related infrastructure (mobility and logistics hubs, traffic management centres, charging infrastructure) and widely demonstrated in 4 cities (Amsterdam, Munich, Limassol, Tampere). 6 follower cities (Athens, Krakow, Gonzo, Milan, Miskolc, Paris region)
Teaser	- Governance models
metaCCAZE accelerates the user-centred deployment of smart systems and services that combine electric automated and connected mobility and related infrastructure across European cities. metaCCAZE organizes a series of MetaDesign activities with multisector-stakeholders and...	
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101139678	
Project end date	
31/12/2027	
Project #36	
Project acronym	
MOBILITIES FOR EU	
Title	
New MOBility solutions for climate neutrality in EU cities	-CCAM Scenarios and use cases: Leading the charge are Madrid and Dresden, implementing 11 pilots with 27 solutions using electrification, automation, and connectivity. These Lead Cities aspire to pioneer the transformation, establishing Urban Transport Labs as Innovation Hubs. Five Replication Cities (Ioannina-Greece, Trencin-Slovakia, Espoo-Finland, Gdansk-Poland and Sarajevo-Bosnia&Herzegovina) will follow suit, participating in the upscaling, and becoming protagonists of their own designs.
Teaser	
MOBILITIES FOR EU aims at demonstrating that innovative passenger mobility and freight transport concepts designed and implemented following participative and user-center principles are cost-effective and feasible solutions to contribute significantly to the cities'...	
URL	
https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101139666	
Project end date	
31/12/2028	

B. ABBREVIATIONS AND DEFINITIONS

Term	Definition
AV	Automated Vehicles
CAV	Connected and Automated Vehicle
CCAM	Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
GA	Grant Agreement
GA	Grant Agreement
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KR	Key Results
KRs	Key Results
ML	Machine Learning
ODD	Operational Design Domain
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
REA	European Research Executive Agency
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
SRIA	Strategic Research & Innovation Agenda
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UC	Use Case
WP	Work Package
XiL	X-in-the-loop